

absorption which could be ascribed to the presence of either coordinated or lattice water. The characteristic bands of these complexes can easily be distinguished from each other from their IR spectra. The $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ frequency of SHA has been found to shift from 1620 to 1601 cm^{-1} in case of sodium salt whereas for the rare earth complexes a shift towards lower frequencies (1600 cm^{-1} for La^{3+} - to Eu^{3+} -complexes) has been observed. The anhydrous complex (anhydrous Sm-salicylhydroxamate) shows still further shift to 1590 cm^{-1} . The CN and NO frequencies of the free ligand shows strong bands at 1560 and 910 cm^{-1} respectively and these were displaced to 1550 and 915 cm^{-1} respectively upon complex formation. The CN band shift towards lower frequency regions whereas the NO frequency shows a shift towards higher frequency region in these complexes. A polymeric structure as obtained in the case of corresponding rare earth salicylate⁹ seems to be probable, in which each metal ion is probably attached to two coordination sites ($-\text{C}=\text{O}$ and NHO^-) in each salicylhydroxamate ions in a polymeric fashion and the coordinate $-\text{C}=\text{O} \cdots \text{Ln}-\text{O}-$ bonds¹⁰ of the lanthanosalicylhydroxamates would be expected to confer covalent character on the compound and thus reduce its electrical conductivity considerably which is corroborated by the conductivity data (Table 1). However, phenolic ($-\text{OH}$) group was remaining free. When the complexes in acetone suspension was treated with neutral FeCl_3 solution, a reddish violet colour developed¹¹. Moreover, in strongly alkaline medium, the complexes were found to be soluble, probably due to the formation of charged complex species as has been observed in the case of salicylic acid¹² and salicylhydroxamic acid¹³.

Electronic spectra: The electronic spectra of the compounds were recorded in which the maximum absorptions have been observed at 198 and 204 nm (in hydrated Ce^{3+} salicylhydroxamate), 530, 550, 560 and 580 nm (in hydrated Nd^{3+} -salicylhydroxamate), 378, 390, 396, 402 nm (in hydrated Sm^{3+} -salicylhydroxamate) and 385, 404 nm (in hydrated Eu^{3+} -salicylhydroxamate).

References

1. A. K. CHAKRABURTTY, Proceedings of the Symposium on Coordination Compound, Part III, Agra (India) p. 235, 1959.
2. J. XAVIER, A. K. CHAKRABURTTY and P. RAY, *Sci. & Cult.*, 1954, 20, 46.
3. C. K. PAL and A. K. CHAKRABURTTY, *Separation Science*, 1974, 9, 71.
4. S. K. BRAHMA and A. K. CHAKRABURTTY, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1977, 39, 1723.
5. S. P. SINHA, *Eurpium*, p. 52, Springer, New York, 1967.
6. C. MUSANTE, *Gazz. Chim., Ital.*, 1948, 78, 536.
7. VAN VLÛCK, *Electric and Magnetic Susceptibilities*, p. 243, Oxford University Press, New York.
8. V. N. KRISHNAMURTHY and S. SOUNDARARAJAN, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1967, 45, 189.
9. J. H. BURNS and W. H. BALDWIN, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1977, 16, 289.
10. N. S. POLUKTOV, R. S. LAUER and V. T. MISCHENKO, *Zh. Anal. Khim.*, (Russ), 1969, 24, 1665.

11. N. N. GHOSH and ARUNA BHATTACHARYA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1964, 41, 311.
12. Y. A. FIALKOV and V. I. ERMOLENKO, *Russ. J. Inorg. Chem., (Eng. Trans)*, 1959, 4, 159, 615.
13. A. K. CHAKRABURTTY, Unpublished work.

Complexes of Titanium Tetrachloride with 8-Quinolinol-N-Oxide

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STUDIES of reactions of 8-quinolinol-N-oxide (HOQNO) for complexing purposes in non-aqueous media, have been very few, except for the report of formation of an adduct with SnCl_4 and disubstituted derivatives with SnCl_4 and TiCl_4 . It appeared that such reactions have not been sufficiently investigated. Present work was taken up to investigate in detail the reaction between TiCl_4 and 8-quinolinol-N-oxide.

Experimental

All operations were carried out under anhydrous conditions. 8-Quinolinol-N-oxide was prepared by the reported method².

Infrared spectra of the products formed were recorded in the region 4000-200 cm^{-1} (in KBr) on Perkin-Elmer Infracord, Model-621, spectrophotometer. Satisfactory elemental analyses were obtained for the compounds (Table 1).

Preparation of the adducts: A benzene solution of 8-quinolinol-N-oxide (in 1 and 2 mole ratios respectively) was added to a well stirred benzene solution of TiCl_4 . The red precipitate so obtained in each case was filtered, washed with chloroform and vacuum dried.

Preparation of $\text{TiCl}_2(\text{OQNO})_2$: A benzene solution of 8-quinolinol-N-oxide was added to a benzene solution of TiCl_4 (1:1, 2:1 and 4:1 mole ratios respectively) and the resulting insoluble product in each case was subjected to refluxing without further isolation until the evolution of hydrogen chloride ceased. The red coloured insoluble product was filtered, washed and dried. In each case, the end product was found to be the same and its analysis corresponded to $\text{TiCl}_2(\text{OQNO})_2$.

$\text{TiCl}_2(\text{OQNO})_2$ is also formed at room temperature when 8-quinolinol-N-oxide and TiCl_4 are mixed in the mole ratio 4:1 and kept till the evolution of hydrogen chloride ceased.

Thermogravimetric (TG) analysis: The TG analysis of 1:1 and 1:2 adducts were carried on Setaram G-70 Thermoanalyser in a stream of nitrogen. The results of TG analysis corresponded

TABLE 1—ELEMENTAL ANALYSIS OF TITANIUM CHELATES OF 8-QUINOLINOL-N-OXIDE%

Compound	C		H		Ti		Cl		N	
	Found	Calcd.								
TiCl ₄ .HOQNO	30.6	30.76	1.94	1.99	13.5	13.67	40.4	40.45	3.9	3.98
TiCl ₄ .2HOQNO	42.00	42.18	2.6	2.7	9.4	9.37	27.8	27.7	5.4	5.46
TiCl ₃ (OQNO) ₂	49.00	49.2	2.6	2.73	11.1	10.9	16.1	16.17	6.3	6.38

to the following schemes of thermal decomposition :

Results and Discussion

The ir spectra of all the complexes were found to be identical with one another but differed from that of the pure ligand. These complexes show a broad band at 3600-3140 cm⁻¹ with a maximum at 3380 cm⁻¹, indicating the presence of an intramolecular hydrogen bonding. The quinoline ring shows the usual absorption bands⁸.

The shifts in the absorption frequencies of diagnostic value, namely N-O stretching, N-O bending and C-H out-of-plane bending, on complexation are discussed below.

N-O stretching frequency: A sharp band at 1310 cm⁻¹ in 8-quinolinol-N-oxide has been assigned to be a N-O stretching frequency¹. In the complexes, the N-O stretching frequency is observed as a very sharp band at 1320 cm⁻¹ as compared to 1310 cm⁻¹ in the free ligand. This significant positive shift can be taken as a measure of back bonding in the complexes reported here^{4,5}.

N-O bending vibrations: The N-O bending vibration in the aromatic amine oxides has been assigned in 900-800 cm⁻¹ region. The N-O bending vibration in quinoline-N-oxide appears as a sharp band at 870 cm⁻¹, which on complexation shifts to 840 cm⁻¹. 8-Quinolinol-N-oxide shows a broad and sharp band at 870 cm⁻¹ with a shoulder at 885 cm⁻¹. Some previous investigators¹ have reported that a sharp band at 810 cm⁻¹ in the free ligand is due to N-O bending modes, probably coupled with a C-H out-of-plane deformation. Since such a sharp band at 810 cm⁻¹ is also present in quinoline and 8-quinolinol⁸ (due to C-H out-of-plane deformation) it appears that the sharp band at 810 cm⁻¹ in 8-quinolinol-N-oxide is unlikely to be due to N-O bending modes. On the basis of deuteration studies, they¹ treated the band at 870 cm⁻¹ shown by 8-quinolinol-N-oxide

to be due to -OH bending modes. As the N-O group is already chelated, a further metallation should result in a decreased bond order for the N-O group and consequently a lower absorption frequency.

In order to resolve this issue we examined 8-quinolinol-N-oxide at high resolution and found that the shouldered band at 870 cm⁻¹ breaks into two sharp bands at 885 cm⁻¹ and 870 cm⁻¹. This could be due to the N-O and O-H bending modes. For further investigation the ligand was deuterated and the product was examined again under high resolution. It showed only one narrow sharp band at 880 cm⁻¹ and another one at 640 cm⁻¹. The band at 640 cm⁻¹ would be due to a shift in the -OH band on deuteration. Thus the band observed in the deuterated ligand and in the undeuterated ligand at 885 cm⁻¹ can be assigned to an N-O bending mode.

C-H out-of-plane deformation: The C-H out-of-plane deformation in the free ligand is observed at 810, 785 and 750 cm⁻¹ as very sharp or medium width bands. In the complexes these shift to 820, 790 and 730 cm⁻¹ respectively, as very sharp bands^{4,5}.

Other bands: In the spectra of these complexes two intense absorption bands are observed at 1050 cm⁻¹ due to quinoline ring vibration¹ and at 1035 cm⁻¹ due to C-O stretching at C-O-M site⁶.

In the far ir region, three medium or sharp bands are observed at 530, 400 and 330 cm⁻¹ which, may be due to Ti-O stretching at Ti-O-C site, Ti-O stretching at Ti-O-N site and Ti-Cl stretching vibrations respectively. This follows from the earlier work reported on metal derivatives of 8-quinolinol⁷ and metal chelates of aromatic amine oxides^{8,9}. Since the complexes now studied show two Ti-O stretching vibrations which may be due to Ti-O-C and Ti-O-N stretchings. This suggest that the ligand acts as a bidentate. In earlier literature it has been stated to act as a monodentate ligand¹.

References

1. K. D. GHUGE, P. UMAPATHY and D. N. SEN, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1978, **55**, 864.
2. K. RAMAIAH and V. R. SRINIVASAN, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci. Sec A*, 1962, **55**, 360.
3. H. SHINDO, *Chem. Pharma. Bull.*, Japan, 1960, **8**, 845.
4. S. KIDA, J. V. QUAGLIANO, J. A. WALMSLEY and S. Y. TYRRE, *Spectrochim. Acta*, 1963, **19**, 189.
5. Y. KAKIUTI, S. KIDA and J. V. QUAGLIANO, *Spectrochim. Acta*, 1963, **19**, 201.
6. R. G. CHARLES, H. FRIESER, R. FRIEDEL, L. E. HILLIARD and W. D. JOHNSTON, *Spectrochim. Acta*, 1956, **8**, 1.

7. T. TANAKA, M. KUMURA and R. OKAWARA, *J. Organometal Chem.*, 1964, 1, 481.
8. S. A. BOYD, R. E. KOHRMAN and D. X. WEST, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1976, 38, 1605.
9. A. N. SPECA, L. S. GELFAND, L. P. PYTLEWSKI, C. OWENS and N. M. KARAYNNIS, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1976, 15, 1493.

Potentiometric Studies of Oxidation of Carbohydrate (Glucose, Galactose, Arabinose, Ribose and Xylose)

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THE determination of carbohydrates with periodic acid has been attempted, both by visual and potentiometric methods. It has been found, however that the potentiometric method (being successful only by the direct procedure with the reductant in the cell) was useful only in conjunction with visual procedure.

The carbohydrates have been determined by a number of methods¹⁻⁵ but no work seems to have been done to determine these compounds by periodate using potentiometric methods. Here, the determinations of these compounds, both by visual and potentiometric methods, have been attempted by the authors.

Below is given a summary of the results obtained of oxidation of glucose, galactose, arabinose, ribose and xylose with periodate, both by visual and potentiometric methods (Table 1).

TABLE 1

Sl. No.	Compound	Compound taken gm	Compound found by visual titration method (gm)	Compound found by potentiometric method (gm)
1.	Glucose	0.02252	0.02246	0.02218
2.	Galactose	0.02251	0.02245	0.02248
3.	Arabinose	0.01877	0.01875	0.01892
4.	Ribose	0.01978	0.01876	0.01882
5.	Xylose	0.01977	0.01878	0.01892

The results show that in the cases of oxidation of glucose, galactose, arabinose, ribose and xylose, comparable results were obtained by visual and potentiometric titration methods.

References

1. P. FLEURY, JEAN COURTOIS and AYWICTSTROM, *Aron Pharm. France*, 1919, 7, 288; *Ch. Chem. Abs.*, 1949, 43, 5399.
2. S. J. ANGYAI and J. E. KLAVINS, *Austral. J. Chem.*, 1961, 14577.
3. NILOTPAL BHATACHARYA and M. L. SEN GUPTA, *Indian. J. Chem.*, 1967, 5, 554.
4. MYRON BRIN, *Israel, J. Med. Sci.*, 1967, 3, 792.
5. I. R. L. BARKER, W. G. OVEREND and C. W. REES, *Chem. Ed. Ind. London*, 1960, 1298.

A Rapid Method for the Estimation of Isoniazid with Dichloramine-T and Dichloramine-B

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ISONIAZID (pyridine-4-carboxylic acid hydrazide), a well-known antituberculosis drug, can be assayed through a number of titrimetric and potentiometric methods and most of them are based on the oxidation of the hydrazide group to nitrogen, except the nitrite method¹ which depends on a diazotisation reaction. A recently published method² is based on the indirect potentiometric determination of isoniazid with a chloramine-T ion selective electrode.

In continuation of our work on oxidation studies with organic chloramines²⁻³, the present paper reports a detailed investigation of the reaction of isoniazid with dichloramine-T (DCT) and dichloramine-B (DCB) in partially aqueous medium. Isoniazid can be oxidized by DCT and DCB with a four electron change within five minutes, when an excess of oxidant is present in the reaction mixture. Direct titration (visual or potentiometric in presence of KBr in acid medium) of isoniazid with the oxidants was found to be slow and not practicable. Hence, a back titration procedure was employed. The procedure described here is simple, rapid and accurate and can be successfully employed for the determination of isoniazid in pharmaceutical products.

Experimental

Reagents: Recrystallized isoniazid (Koch-light, England) was used. Solution of isoniazid in triply distilled water was standardized⁴. DCT was prepared by the method of Jacob and Nair¹⁰. Chlorination of aqueous solution of chloramine-B⁴ gives good samples of DCB⁶. Approximately decinormal solutions of DCT and DCB were prepared in glacial acetic acid containing 10% v/v acetic anhydride and were standardized by the iodometric method. All other reagents were of accepted grades of purity.

Preliminary studies: Known aliquots of isoniazid solution were added to a known excessive volume of DCT or DCB in an iodine flask at room temperature (30°). The reaction mixture was set aside for various intervals of time with occasional shaking and the maximum standing time being one hour. Then the excess of DCT or DCB was determined by iodometric back titration. It was found that the oxidation of isoniazid was rapid and stoichiometric within five minutes, by an excess of either of the oxidant.

Recommended procedure: Take a sample containing 4-40 mg of isoniazid and dissolve it in 10-15 ml of water. Add the aqueous solution to 25 ml of